

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY CLASSES

Quvvatov Rahmatullo Hikmatullayevich

Pedagogical Institute of Termez State University

quvvatovrahmatullo40@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675373>

Annotation: This article provides information about the development of students' logical thinking skills in teaching English in primary classes, the fluency of speech, the formation of skills for quick and correct answers, the enthusiasm for knowledge, the desire to thoroughly prepare for lessons.

Keywords: Beginner, Game, educational, education,

Today, there is no need to assess the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our country, for which the world community is trying to occupy a worthy place, for our people who are building their great future in cooperation and cooperation with our foreign partners."

In particular, one of the decisions that caused positive changes in primary education was the decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "on measures for further improvement of the Foreign Language Learning System" PP-1875 . According to this decision , in order to further increase their interest in teaching foreign languages , mainly English, starting from the primary school, teaching them foreign languages, starting from the 1st grade in all secondary schools, the teaching of English lessons in different ways of interesting games, and at the same time the development of oral speech by students, starting from the 2nd grade, Recently, the number of people at any age who learn English is growing very much. This is because in the process of life it is becoming more difficult to live without knowledge of English. But language learning also depends on age periods. Even scientists have proven that children absorb things quickly and easily than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency to language learning in children, the fact that they have a strong imitation feature, the abundance of children's time compared to adults and the rapid storage of learned information. Undoubtedly, equipping the rooms of foreign languages with modern information and communication technologies and advanced technical means of teaching foreign languages in the educational halls of our country, giving broadcasts and broadcasts in TV channels teaching children and adolescents foreign languages, regularly showing scientific and popular foreign feature films dedicated to the history and culture of other countries, World Science and technical innovations, it made it possible to get acquainted with science more closely. When teaching foreign languages to students in primary classes, especially in the first class, it is necessary to take

into account the age, physiologic, psychological characteristics of the student. The use of gaming technologies in education is one of the most effective tools. During the game, their thinking, worldview, thinking become clear. Scientists believe that the approach through the game to education facilitates the educational process. Not only does it make it easier, but it also encourages interest in science kuchaytirib, the child to gain in-depth knowledge. Lessons in the style of play contribute to the development of children's oral speech. First-graders are very fond of different views with pictures or video. It is necessary to regularly use games in the cultivation of their speeches, through different colored pictures. For example, what is it?, Who is this?, Who knows many words?" can be used in games like. In the process of the game, it is necessary to encourage children to remember words, depending on the correct pronunciation. Depending on the increase in the vocabulary of children, it is also important to organize other types of games, various competitions. Children can initially perform exercises on such topics as "fruit names", "professions", "home appliances" with the help of games. Then, when they are displayed in a state of harmony with the colorful images on the computer, the reader's speech develops and the circle of attitude towards the environment abounds. At the stage of displaying a new topic, words and pictures reflecting it appear on the screen. Students will be able to listen to the words and pronounce them. When presenting the topic with the help of a computer, it is necessary to pay attention to the print-out of individualization of Education. Some readers find it difficult to perceive the graphic of the word, and some-the image with a vowel. The computer eliminates this or that difficulty in the means of the exercise and helps the student to find out the aspects of the difficulty in mastering the English language and eliminate them. Starting from the second grade, other educational games aimed at mastering mathematics can also be organized. For example, "who is a literate?" , Who is clever?, "Who am I? Such interesting games as " find the place of the word", " chain", "roll game", " shular are in the sentence. "Who is clever? "the game gives a good result in improving spelling literacy. In this, 5-6 words are written on a cardboard sheet, the words will be correct and written incorrectly. Readers are asked to find the wrong word and write it correctly. Depending on which reader correctly and first writes the wrong words, the winner of the game is determined. As we know, current education should be a subject of study. Bunda focusing on more interactive techniques will increase the effectiveness of Education. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach independent thinking. To be remembered by sight . It

is known that young children remember their subjects, which they saw more often than they heard. Therefore, the lesson is taught by various visual weapons, posters, something visible and often used in everyday life, writing on objects, teaching new words and making sentences with the participation of new words learned . For example, writing to book (book), table (table), whiteboard (blackboard), Pen (pen), Window (window), etc. Such a thing, which is often used in everyday life-the child learns these words in an involuntary way, since the object is constantly falling into the eye and constantly applied.

Through songs and poems, to put words that are difficult to understand or Remember into music and sing. In addition to remembering new words in Bunda, the verbal speech of the child develops. An example of this can be shown that the children's learning of the English alphabet by singing is more effective than simply memorizing . In fact, language learning through sensory organs is more useful and effective than other methods . For example, the reader in the process of tasting only one Apple knows what its color, taste, size, smell is and also says its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the children for the English name of the colors, they immediately remember the time when the children ate the fruit. This means that the use of such methods will help the reader to keep the data in his memory in the long term. The interest in mastering the foreign language in them, taking into account the young and psychological characteristics of students in the teaching of English, the preparation of modern didactic works based on pedagogical technologies that help to fully meet the need and the development of a solid framework of their implementation will provide a practical solution of muaommo.

Not as an obligation to teach a language to a primary school student, but rather as a result of using fun games and innovative techniques can serve as the foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, as the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, harmonious, mature personality, in the future, we will be able to make our own contribution with the further development of ways of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers .

Used literature:

1. Turdaliyeva G.N "modern approaches and innovations in teaching English in primary classes" // 2020 .
2. She Is A Gentleman.B. "Use of innovative technologies in teaching English" / / Tashkent 2012.
3. Toliboboeva, S. J. (2020). teaching intercultural communication in english. ScienceandEducation,

4. Toliboboeva, Sh. (2020). Modern educational technologies in teaching English.

